

SMART ERA PROJECT - EIP AGRI PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

REVITALISING LOCAL RURAL COMMUNITIES THROUGH DIGITAL PLATFORMS

Northern Ostrobothnia is a largely rural region of Finland facing **demographic and structural challenges**. Many areas are experiencing **population decline and limited access to services**, which is putting **pressure on local businesses**. The ageing population and the centralisation of services have made it more difficult for residents, particularly the elderly and those without private transport, to access everyday services. At the same time, rural entrepreneurs often struggle to reach new customers and traditional channels may no longer suffice. However, **digitalisation and the rise of remote working** present **new opportunities** to invigorate local economies and communities.

Against this backdrop, a **centrally operated digital service platform is being developed and tested in the municipalities of Alavieska, Kalajoki, and Nivala**. The platform **connects local service providers** from various sectors, such as tourism operators, cultural organisations, and care services, more efficiently **with residents, remote workers, and visitors**. Rather than offering services itself, the platform functions as a **digital meeting point** where supply and demand can more easily match. Inspired by services such as Airbnb and Uber, this model is tailored to local needs and is available for use by small-scale entrepreneurs and communities.

Workshops with residents and service providers have revealed strong interest in easier access to local services and better visibility for providers. The platform's key characteristics include ease of use, safety, access to up-to-date information, and a diverse range of services.

GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION

Providers benefit from increased reach and visibility at a low cost, while users gain convenient access to relevant services. Social cohesion and local networks are recognised as strengths to build upon.

Development will continue in 2025, with pilot implementation planned for 2026. The model is scalable and can support rural economies, entrepreneurship and quality of life in other regions.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Facilitating elements: High local interest, strong sense of community, and willingness of municipalities to support coordination and onboarding.

Obstacles: Initial awareness-raising is needed.

Future actions: Continued co-development with users; **piloting** the platform in real-world conditions in 2026.

Messages to end-users:

- Local service providers: Listing your services on the platform can **expand your customer base with minimal effort or cost.**
- Residents and remote workers: Use the platform to easily discover services in your area and **support local businesses.**
- Municipalities and community organisations: Consider adopting and tailoring the model to **support rural development and service access in your area.**

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

[Northern Ostrobothnia, Finland website](#)

[Municipality of Alavieska website](#)

[City of Kalajoki website](#)

[City of Nivala website](#)

Image by Heikki Saari

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